

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

IR-Kesar: a brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant variety for Cambodia

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Early rice varieties with duration of less than 120 d are grown during wet season (WS) as normal and August-seeded crops. They are grown during dry season (DS) as water-receding crops, which are seeded from Oct to Jan with no or partial irrigation, and as normal DS crops under full irrigation during Jan-Mar.

Most of the varieties planted are photoperiod-insensitive modern ones, the most popular of which are IR36, IR42, and IR50. During the past 3 yr, IR66,

IR72, and Kru have been spreading quickly. Weakly photoperiod-sensitive traditional varieties are also grown.

BPH is a serious pest during DS and occasionally during WS. Varietal resistances of IR36, IR42, and IR66 are no longer effective against BPH. Kru and IR72 are only the moderately resistant varieties available, thus the need for additional resistant varieties was realized.

Breeding line IR48525-100-1-2 was introduced to Cambodia from IRRI in 1989. The line is a cross of advanced breeding lines IR24632-34-2 and IR31868-64-2-3-3-3. The superior performance of IR48525-100-1-2 was observed in various trials in both DS and WS since 1990 (Table 1). IR48525-100-1-2 yielded as much as IR50, IR66, IR72,

and Kru. Under serious BPH infestation, however, IR48525-100-1-2 outperformed other varieties (Table 2). It also has some resistance to leaffolder, gall midge, and stem borer. IR48525-100-1-2 was named IR-Kesar and recommended for testing at more than 190 locations in Cambodia during 1993. ■

Table 2. Performance of IR-Kesar (IR48525-100-1-2) in advanced yield trial at Prey Phdau (Kampong Speu Province) Research Station under severe BPH infestation. 1991 DS.

Entry	Yield (t/ha)	BPH score ^a (0-9)
IR48525-100-1-2	4.0	1.5
IR48563-123-5-5-2	1.7	6.5
IR48613-21-3-2-2	2.9	2.5
IR50363-8-1-1-3	2.4	7.0
IR50363-61-1-2-2	1.9	6.5
IR51008-89-2-1-2	2.6	3.5
IR51009-58-1-1-2	1.8	5.5
IR52280-64-3-3-3	1.7	6.5
IR52256-203-2-2-3	1.6	6.0
Kru (check)	3.3	2.2
Mean	2.4	4.8

^aScored using the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Table 1. Performance of IR-Kesar (IR48525-100-1-2) and checks for seedling vigor, duration, height, BPH damage score, phenotypic acceptability (PAcp), and yield in various trials. Cambodia, 1990-92.

	PYT, ^a 1990 DS (2 locations)		PYT, early ^b 1990 (2 locations)		
	IR-Kesar	IR50	IR-Kesar	IR66	IR72
Vigor	-	-	4.0	6.0	7.0
Duration (d)	116	105	118	110	118
Height (cm)	94	76	93	89	81
PAcp	4.5	5.5	4.5	4.5	4.0
Yield (t/ha)	3.8	3.2	5.3	4.4	4.2
	AYT, ^c 1991 DS (10 locations)		AYT, early 1991 (14 locations)		
	IR-Kesar	Kru	IR-Kesar	Kru	
Vigor	2.8	3.0	3.0	3.6	
Duration (d)	116	113	115	113	
Height (cm)	86	80	87	84	
PAcp			2.5	2.5	
BPH ^d	1.5	2.2			
Yield (t/ha)	4.74	4.68	4.20	4.46	
	AYT, 1992 DS (9 locations)		AYT, early 1992 (17 locations)		
	IR-Kesar	Kru	IR-Kesar	Kru	
Vigor	1.8	2.8	3.7	3.7	
Duration (d)	114	108	122	114	
Height (cm)	88	83	79	78	
PAcp	3.0	4.3	3.3	3.6	
BPH ^d	0.3	1.5	-	-	
Yield (t/ha)	4.37	4.32	2.8	2.7	

^aPYT = preliminary yield trial. ^bEarly season = Jan-Mar. ^cAYT = advanced yield trial. ^dScored using the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Lioto, a short-duration rice variety suitable for northern Zaire

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Farmers tend to grow maize, peanut, and cotton rather than rice during the first cropping season (Apr-Aug) in Bambesa Zone of northern Zaire to avoid severe damage to the rice crop by birds and big rodents (*Thryonomys swinderianus*) called simbiliki. Rice is grown with fewer problems during the second season (Sep-Dec) when rain is often inadequate. Varieties such as IRAT112 have a short growth duration and are appropriate for late planting during the second season.

IRAT112 (RY150) has been cultivated in Bambesa Zone since 1985 because of its short growth duration (110 d) and

Table 1. Plant characteristics of 4 selected breeding lines at Bambosa, Zaire, 1989-91.

Characteristic	Line/variety					
	R66	PR36-1-3-1	PR36-1-7-2	PR36-1-2-2	PR36-1-1-2	IRAT112 (check)
Life cycle (d)	124	116	116	116	115	115
Plant height (cm)	145	110	92	107	104	80
Lodging (score) ^a	3	1	1	1	1	1
Grain length (mm)	9.20	9.89	9.51	9.77	9.51	9.55
Grain width (mm)	2.98	3.24	3.07	3.12	3.07	2.88
Grain thickness (mm)	2.15	2.40	2.28	2.35	2.28	2.83
L-W ratio	3.08	3.05	3.09	3.13	3.09	3.32
W-T ratio	1.30	1.35	1.35	1.32	1.35	1.02
1,000-grain weight (g)	31.8	37.2	30.0	32.0	30.0	31.90
Translucency (%)	81.7	73.6	77.8	75.0	79.5	72.4
Disease reaction ^a						
Leaf blast	MS	MR	MR	MR	MR	MR
Leaf scald	MR	R	R	R	R	R
Grain yield (t/ha)	2.7	3.2	3.0	2.8	2.8	2.9

^aScored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Table 2. Performance of 4 selected breeding lines at 3 locations. Zaire, 1989-91.

Location	Grain yield ^a (t/ha) and increase over check IRAT112 (%)									
	IRAT112 (check)		PR36-1-3-1		PR36-1-7-2		PR36-1-2-2		PR36-1-1-2	
	t/ha	%	t/ha	%	t/ha	%	t/ha	%	t/ha	%
Yangambi	2.8		2.8	3	2.7	0	2.5	-8	2.4	-13
Bambosa	2.9		3.2	11	3.0	4	2.8	-1	2.8	-1
Kiyaka	2.6		2.9	11	2.1	-10	2.8	10	2.9	11
Av	2.7		2.9	8	2.6	-5	2.7	1	2.7	-1

^aYield is av of 3 yr.

good grain quality. It resists blast and leaf scald and yields an average of 2.8 t/ha. The short stature (80 cm) of IRAT112, however, makes the common practice of hand harvesting difficult for tall farmers, who must stoop to harvest panicles. The result is that they tire quickly. They prefer a medium-height (100-140 cm) variety that is tolerant of lodging.

Local cultivar R66 was crossed with IRAT112 at Yangambi Research Station with the aim of creating a medium-height, lodging-tolerant, short-duration variety with good grain characteristics. Four breeding lines were selected from R66/IRAT112 and compared with IRAT112 at three sites (Yangambi, Bambosa, Kiyaka) from 1989 to 1991 (Table 1). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Plots were 3 × 5 m, in

which 4-5 grains/hill were sown at 25 × 20-cm spacing.

At the Bambosa site, yield potential, life cycle, lodging tolerance, and reaction to leaf blast and leaf scald were similar for the breeding lines and IRAT112 (Table 1). Grain quality characteristics of the breeding lines, except for 1,000-grain weight, were also comparable with those of IRAT112. PR36-1-3-1 had an advantage over all other materials tested for 1,000-grain weight. Plant height, however, varied among lines, with PR36-1-3-1 averaging 110 cm. Performance of PR36-1-3-1 was good and yields stable across three locations (Table 2).

PR36-1-3-1 was released as Lioto to replace IRAT112. Increased plant height and tolerance for lodging are its major advantages over IRAT112. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Brazilian Upland Rice Breeding Network: varietal release, time span, and yield increase

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The state rice research institutions of Brazil formed the Upland Rice Breeding Network in 1982 to develop suitable upland rice varieties for the country's different regions. The National Rice and Beans Research Center (CNPAP) coordinates the network.

Twelve upland varieties released between 1985 and 1989 were analyzed for time between crossing and varietal release, time required for yield trials, and average increase in grain yield of new materials compared with previously released varieties. Our primary information sources were publications containing data from varietal release trials prepared by state research institutions and CNPAF.

Time between crossing and varietal release averaged 8.8 yr (Table 1). The first variety released, Cuiabana, required

Table 1. Varieties released to the Brazilian Cerrados Region by the Upland Rice Breeding Network, 1985-89.^a

Variety	YC	YR	TD	YT	TY
Araguaia	1978	1987	9	1983	4
BR-4	1976	1985	9	1981	4
Cabaçu	1979	1988	9	1985	3
C. América	1978	1987	9	1983	4
Cuiabana	1978	1985	7	1983	2
Douradão	1978	1989	11	1986	3
EMCAPA 01	1976	1985	9	1981	4
Guaporé	1980	1988	8	1985	3
Guarani	1978	1987	9	1983	4
Rio Paranaíba	1978	1987	9	1984	3
Tangará	1981	1989	8	1985	4
Xingu	1980	1989	9	1986	3
Mean			8.8		3.4

^aYC = year of crossing, YR = year of release, TD = number of years from crossing to release, YT = year of trial, TY = number of years under yield trials.